

ON THE CLASSIFICATION OF SOME CLASSES OF DOPPELSEMIGROUPS UP TO ISOMORPHISM

V. M. Gavrylkiv

Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine

vgavrylkiv@gmail.com

A *doppelsemigroup* [5, 8] is an algebraic structure (D, \dashv, \vdash) consisting of a non-empty set D equipped with two associative binary operations \dashv and \vdash satisfying the following axioms:

$$(D_1) \quad (x \dashv y) \vdash z = x \dashv (y \vdash z),$$

$$(D_2) \quad (x \vdash y) \dashv z = x \vdash (y \dashv z).$$

A doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv, \vdash) is called *commutative* [6] if both semigroups (D, \dashv) and (D, \vdash) are commutative. A doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv, \vdash) is said to be *strong* [7] if it satisfies the axiom

$$x \dashv (y \vdash z) = x \vdash (y \dashv z).$$

Each semigroup (S, \dashv) can be consider as a (strong) doppelsemigroup (S, \dashv, \dashv) , and we denote this *trivial* doppelsemigroup by S . Let (D, \dashv, \vdash) be a doppelsemigroup. Denote by $(D, \dashv, \vdash)^d$ its *dual* doppelsemigroup (D, \dashv^d, \vdash^d) , where $x \dashv^d y = y \dashv x$ and $x \vdash^d y = y \vdash x$. It follows that $(D, \dashv, \vdash)^d$ is a (strong) doppelsemigroup if and only if (D, \dashv, \vdash) is a (strong) doppelsemigroup. Therefore, non-commutative doppelsemigroups are divided into the pairs of dual doppelsemigroups.

One of the main tasks in the study of algebraic structures is their classification up to isomorphism. In [3], the task of describing all pairwise non-isomorphic (strong) doppelsemigroups of order 3 has been solved.

Theorem 1. *There exist 75 pairwise non-isomorphic three-element doppelsemigroups among which 41 doppelsemigroups are commutative. Non-commutative doppelsemigroups are divided into 17 pairs of dual doppelsemigroups. Also up to isomorphism there are 65 strong doppelsemigroups of order 3, and all non-strong doppelsemigroups are not commutative. There exist exactly 24 pairwise non-isomorphic three-element trivial doppelsemigroups.*

A doppelsemigroup (G, \dashv, \vdash) is called a *group doppelsemigroup* if (G, \dashv) is a group. It follows that (G, \vdash) is a group isomorphic to (G, \dashv) , see [1, 2].

Proposition 1. *Let (G, \dashv) be a group and let (G, \dashv, \vdash) be a doppelsemigroup. Then $\vdash = \dashv_a$ for some $a \in G$.*

Corollary 1. *Let (G, \dashv) be an Abelian group and let (G, \dashv, \vdash) be a doppelsemigroup. Then (G, \dashv, \vdash) is a commutative strong doppelsemigroup and $\vdash = \dashv_a$ for some $a \in G$.*

Recall that the number of divisors function $\tau(n)$ is defined as the number of natural divisors of a natural number n .

A doppelsemigroup (G, \dashv, \vdash) said to be *cyclic* if (G, \dashv) is a cyclic group. The following theorems on the number of pairwise non-isomorphic cyclic doppelsemigroups were proved by the author, see [4].

Theorem 2. *There exist $\tau(n)$ pairwise non-isomorphic finite cyclic doppelsemigroups of order n . All finite cyclic doppelsemigroups are strong and commutative.*

Theorem 3. *Let $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$. The doppelsemigroups $(\mathbb{Z}, +, +_a)$ and $(\mathbb{Z}, +, +_b)$ are isomorphic if and only if $b \in \{a, -a\}$. Consequently, there exist countably infinite many pairwise non-isomorphic infinite cyclic (commutative strong) doppelsemigroups.*

1. Boyd S.J., Gould M., Nelson A. Interassociativity of Semigroups. Proceedings of the Tennessee Topology Conference, World Scientific., 1997, 33–51.
2. Drouzy M. La structuration des ensembles de semigroupes d'ordre 2, 3 et 4 par la relation d'interassociativité, manuscript, 1986.
3. Gavrylkiv V.M., Rendziak D.V. Interassociativity and three-element doppelsemigroups. Algebra Discrete Math., 2019, 28, 2, 224–247.
4. Gavrylkiv V. Note on cyclic doppelsemigroups. Algebra Discrete Math., 2022, 34, 1, 15–21.
5. Zhuchok A.V., Demko M. Free n -dinilpotent doppelsemigroups. Algebra Discrete Math., 2016, 22, 2, 304–316.
6. Zhuchok A.V. Free products of doppelsemigroups. Algebra Univers., 2017, 77, 3, 361–374.
7. Zhuchok A.V. Structure of free strong doppelsemigroups. Commun. Algebra, 2018, 46, 8, 3262–3279.
8. Zhuchok A.V. Relatively free doppelsemigroups. Monograph series Lectures in Pure and Applied Mathematics. Germany, Potsdam: Potsdam University Press., 5, 2018, 86 p.